

A New Method of Conversion of Coumarins to *o*-Coumaric Acids.

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The troublesome method of converting coumarin to *o*-coumaric acid by boiling with a very concentrated solution of sodium hydroxide or sodium ethoxide was modified by Dodge (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1916, 38, 450) who obtained *o*-coumaric acid from coumarin by warming its bisulphite compound with 50 per cent. potassium hydroxide solution. Recently Dey and Row (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1924, 125, 561) also obtained various *o*-coumaric acid derivatives from the bisulphite compounds of the corresponding coumarins by boiling with 20 per cent. caustic potash for an hour.

The present paper deals with a new method of effecting readily the same conversion of substituted coumarins, having negative substituents such as nitro-, aldehydo-, iodo-, chloro- and bromo- in the 6-position to *o*-coumaric acid derivatives by means of (a) mercuric oxide (yellow or red) and (b) mercuric acetate, by which coumarin itself also gives a good yield of *o*-coumaric acid. These substituted coumarins, as recorded by Dey and Row (*loc. cit.*), are not easily converted to *o*-coumaric acid derivatives even by boiling with concentrated solutions of sodium hydroxide or sodium ethoxide, which often bring about complicated changes. Though geometrical inversion with the help of chemical reagents (Wislicenus, *Ber.*, 1895, 28, 1080, 2693) and with the help of chemical reactions (Skraup, *Monatsh.*, 1891, 12, 107; Neogi and Chatterji, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 5, 279) is known, no case appears to have been previously studied in which mercury salts have been employed.

When a very dilute alkaline solution (about one per cent.) of these substituted coumarins is boiled for about an hour with a small quantity of yellow or red mercuric oxide, the sodium salts of the coumarinic acids undergo geometrical inversion quantitatively to the salt of the *o*-coumaric acids and the free acids are obtained when the solutions are acidified. In this manner, 5-nitro-, 5-aldehydo-, 5-iodo-, 3:5-dichloro- and 3:5-dibromo-*o*-coumaric acids have easily been obtained from the corresponding coumarins, the iodo- and the aldehydo-*o*-coumaric acids being prepared for the first time.

Control experiments in the absence of mercuric oxide showed that the inversion does not take place. Incidentally it has also been

noticed that oxides of any other metal such as silver, cadmium, copper, calcium, magnesium and iron cannot bring about this inversion. The action of mercuric oxide seems to be purely catalytic as it remains unchanged at the end of the operation.

It is interesting to note that coumarin itself, 4:7-dimethyl coumarin and the hydroxycoumarins (such as β -methylumbelliferone and β -methyldaphnetin) are not inverted but undergo mercuration by similar treatment with mercuric oxide (Sen and Chakravarti, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 847). The influence of a negative substituent in the 6-position in these cases of geometrical inversion to *o*-coumaric acids is confirmed by the fact that 4:6-dimethylcoumarin, in which the 6-position is occupied by a positive substituent, is not converted into the *o*-coumaric acid but is easily mercurated producing a mono-mercury derivative.

Such conversion of 6-nitro-, 6:8-dichloro- and 6:8-dibromocoumarins to the corresponding *o*-coumaric acids also takes place very readily with quantitative yields by adding an aqueous solution of mercuric acetate to a caustic soda solution of the coumarins, neutralised with acetic acid in the cold, dissolving the precipitate formed in cold caustic soda and reprecipitating with hydrochloric acid. In the case of coumarin, however, a dimercury derivative of *o*-coumaric acid has been isolated (Sen and Chakravarti, *loc. cit.*), which when boiled with hydrochloric acid, gives a good yield of *o*-coumaric acid.

Many of these substituted *o*-coumaric acids, like *o*-coumaric acid itself, exhibit a fine blue fluorescence in alkaline solution which is diminished to a slight extent in the case of dichloro- and dibromo-*o*-coumaric acids while it completely vanishes in the case of iodo- and nitro-*o*-coumaric acids.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Inversion with Mercuric Oxide.

5-Nitro-*o*-coumaric Acid.—A solution of 6-nitrocoumarin (5 g.) in caustic soda (4 g. in 100 c. c. water), is diluted with water (300 c. c.) and boiled for about an hour with powdered mercuric oxide (red or yellow, 5 g.). The cold solution is filtered from the mercuric oxide and acidified with hydrochloric acid. The yellow precipitate, thus obtained, is washed with water and dissolved in ammonia. The ammoniacal solution is filtered and acidified with hydrochloric acid and the precipitate filtered, dried and crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless needles decomposing at 245-247° and becoming yellow on

exposure to light. This is identical with the nitro-*o*-coumaric acid described by Dey and Row (*loc. cit.*). (Found: N, 6.4. $C_9H_7O_5N$ requires N, 6.7 per cent.).

5-Aldehydo-o-coumaric Acid.—A solution of 6-aldehydocoumarin (2 g.) in caustic soda (4 g. in 125 c. c. water) is diluted with water (400 c. c.) and boiled for about an hour with mercuric oxide (3 g.). The method of isolation and purification of the compound is the same as in the previous case; crystallised from dilute alcohol, it decomposes at 220°. (Found: C, 62.1; H, 4.40. $C_{10}H_8O_4$ requires C, 62.5; H, 4.16 per cent.).

The *phenylhydrazone*, prepared in the usual manner, is crystallised from dilute acetic acid; it is a yellow substance, decomposes at 237°. (Found: N, 9.8. $C_{16}H_{14}O_3N_2$ requires N, 9.93 per cent.).

The *semicarbazone*, prepared in the usual manner, is crystallised from dilute alcohol; it decomposes at 275°. (Found: N, 16.4. $C_{11}H_{11}O_4N_3$ requires N, 16.87 per cent.).

5-Iodo-o-coumaric Acid.—6-Iodocoumarin (1 g.) is dissolved in a solution of caustic soda (2 g.) in water (50 c. c.) and the solution, diluted with water (200 c. c.) is boiled for half an hour with mercuric oxide (1 g.). The method of isolation and the purification of the compound is the same as described before. It crystallised from diluted alcohol in microcrystalline powder decomposing at 187°. (Found: I, 43.43. $C_9H_7O_3I$ requires I, 43.77 per cent.).

3:5-Dichloro-o-coumaric Acid.—6:8-Dichlorocoumarin (2 g.) is dissolved in a solution of caustic soda (4 g.) in water (25 c. c.) and the alkaline solution diluted with water (400 c. c.), and boiled for half an hour with mercuric oxide (3 g.). The compound is isolated as usual. It is crystallised from dilute alcohol; it decomposes at 242°. It is identical with the dichloro-*o*-coumaric acid of Dey and Row (*loc. cit.*).

3:5-Dibromo-o-coumaric Acid.—It is obtained from 6:8-dibromo-*o*-coumarin in a manner similar to that of the dichloro-compound. It forms needles decomposing at 230° which are identical with the dibromo-*o*-coumaric acid prepared by Dey and Row (*loc. cit.*), who records the melting point as 238°.

Inversion with Mercuric Acetate.

o-Coumaric Acid.—Coumarin (5 g.) is dissolved in caustic soda solution (5 g. in 500 c. c. water) and the cold alkaline solution is carefully neutralised with dilute acetic acid from a burette using

litmus as an indicator. Mercuric acetate (15 g.), dissolved in water (100 c. c.) acidified with acetic acid, is then immediately added from a burette and the solution stirred, when a voluminous precipitate is thrown down. The solution is then left for about half an hour and filtered. The precipitate is washed with cold water, dissolved in dilute caustic potash solution and reprecipitated with acetic acid. The precipitate (diacetoxy-mercuri-*o*-coumaric acid, m.p. 215°, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 6, 852) is boiled with water (300 c. c.) containing concentrated hydrochloric acid (10 c. c.). The boiling solution is filtered hot and the filtrate on cooling gives needle-shaped crystals of *o*-coumaric acid, m.p. 207-209°. (Yield, 3.5 g.).

This *o*-coumaric acid, on treatment with concentrated sulphuric acid on the water-bath, gives coumarin (m.p. 69°).

5-Nitro-*o*-coumaric Acid.—A dilute caustic soda solution of 6-nitrocoumarin (5 g.) is carefully acidified with dilute acetic acid in the cold from a burette using litmus as an indicator and an aqueous solution of mercuric acetate (12 g.) is rapidly added and the solution left for half an hour and filtered. The precipitate is washed with cold water, dissolved in cold dilute caustic potash solution and reprecipitated with hydrochloric acid. The precipitate is filtered off, dried and crystallised from dilute alcohol; decomp. 247°. It is identical with the nitro-*o*-coumaric acid prepared by Dey and Row (*loc. cit.*).

3:5-Dichloro-*o*-coumaric Acid.—It is obtained from 6:8-dichlorocoumarin and the method of preparation and purification of the compound is the same as in the previous case; it decomposes at 242° and is identical with the dichloro-*o*-coumaric acid of Dey and Row (*loc. cit.*).

Dibromo-*o*-coumaric Acid.—It is obtained from 6:8-dibromocoumarin by a similar method.

Mercuration of 4:6-Dimethylcoumarin: Formation of 8-Acetoxy-mercuri-4:6-dimethylcoumarin.—An alkaline solution of 4:6-dimethylcoumarin is boiled with mercuric oxide and the filtered solution acidified with acetic acid, and the precipitate thoroughly washed with water and then with alcohol and dried in a vacuum desiccator. (Found: Hg, 45.80. $C_{13}H_{12}O_4$ Hg. requires Hg, 46.3 per cent.).